

Some notions of purity in *QTAG*-modules

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Abstract: A right module M over an associative ring R with unity is a *QTAG*-module if every finitely generated submodule of any homomorphic image of M is a direct sum of uniserial modules. Motivated by the h -purity and h -purifiability, we study strongly h -purifiability in *QTAG*-modules and obtain several characterizations. Also, some new invariants of *QTAG*-modules are highlighted with the help of h -purifiable submodules and h -pure hulls. It is found that a strongly h -purifiability to be an intersection of finitely many h -pure hulls.

Key words: *QTAG*-modules, quasi h -pure submodules, h -purifiable submodules, h -pure hulls

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

Let R be any ring. A uniserial module M is a module over a ring R , whose submodules are totally ordered by inclusion. This means simply that for any two submodules N_1 and N_2 of M , either $N_1 \subseteq N_2$ or $N_2 \subseteq N_1$. A module M is called a serial module if it is a direct sum of uniserial modules. An element $x \in M$ is uniform, if xR is a non-zero uniform (hence uniserial) module and for any R -module M with a unique decomposition series, $d(M)$ denotes its decomposition length.

Modules are the natural generalizations of abelian groups. Some results on abelian groups hold good for modules if there are certain restrictions on rings and some hold if the modules satisfy certain conditions. A module M_R is called a *TAG*-module if it satisfies the following two conditions:

- (I) Every finitely generated submodule of any homomorphic image of M is a direct sum of uniserial modules.
- (II) Given any two uniserial submodules U and V of a homomorphic image of M , for any submodule W of U , any non-zero homomorphism $f : W \rightarrow V$ can be extended to a homomorphism $g : U \rightarrow V$, provided the composition length $d(U/W) \leq d(V/f(W))$.

A module M_R satisfying only condition (I) is called a *QTAG*-module. The study of *QTAG*-modules and their structure began with work of Singh in [15]. This work, executed by many authors, clearly parallels the earlier work on torsion abelian groups [5, 12, 13, 19]. They developed the theory of *QTAG*-modules by introducing different notions and characterizing them. In the theory of abelian groups many concepts may be generalized for modules. Out of these these concepts purity and purifiability are very fascinating, which have been generalized earlier in [6, 8]. Here we extend these concepts by generalizing strongly purifiability in *QTAG*-modules. Several characterizations of different notions of purity are obtained and as a consequence we

deduce [14, Theorem 3.2] as Theorem 2.2. It is interesting to note that almost all the results which hold for TAG -modules are also valid for $QTAG$ -modules [13]. Many results of this paper are the generalization of [14]. Our notations and terminology generally agree with those in [2] and [3]. For the better understanding of the mentioned topic here one must go through the papers [1, 16, 17].

Everywhere in the text of the present article; let it be agreed that all the rings are associative with unity ($1 \neq 0$) and modules are unital $QTAG$ -modules. For a uniform element $x \in M$, $e(x) = d(xR)$ and $H_M(x) = \sup \left\{ d \left(\frac{yR}{xR} \right) \mid y \in M, x \in yR \text{ and } y \text{ uniform} \right\}$ are the exponent and height of x in M , respectively. $H_n(M)$ denotes the submodule of M generated by the elements of height at least n and $H^n(M)$ is the submodule of M generated by the elements of exponents at most n . A submodule N of M is h -pure [4] in M if $N \cap H_n(M) = H_n(N)$, for every integer $n \geq 0$. The sum of all simple submodules of M is called the socle of M , denoted by $Soc(M)$ and a submodule S of $Soc(M)$ is called a subsocle of M . The cardinality of the minimal generating set of M is denoted by $g(M)$. For all ordinals α , $f_M(\alpha)$ is the α^{th} -Ulm invariant of M (see [9]) and it is equal to $g(Soc(H_\alpha(M))/Soc(H_{\alpha+1}(M)))$. Imitating [10], the submodules $H_n(M), n \geq 0$ form a neighborhood system of zero, thus a topology known as h -topology arises. Closed modules are also closed with respect to this topology. Thus, the closure of $N \subseteq M$ is defined as $\overline{N} = \bigcap_{n=0}^{\infty} (N + H_n(M))$. Therefore, the submodule $N \subseteq M$ is h -dense in M if $\overline{N} = M$.

2. Main Concepts and Results

Firstly, we recall some notations and definitions from [7, 8, 11], respectively.

For any non-negative integer t and for a submodule N of a $QTAG$ -module M , we denote by $N^t(M)$ the submodule $(N + H_{t+1}(M)) \cap Soc(H_t(M))$, by $N_t(M)$ the submodule $(N \cap Soc(H_t(M))) + Soc(H_{t+1}(M))$ and by $Q_t(M, N) = N^t(M)/N_t(M)$.

A submodule N of a $QTAG$ -module M is quasi h -pure in M if $Q_t(M, N) = 0$ for all $t \geq 0$.

If N is quasi h -pure in M , then there exists a maximal quasi h -pure essential extension of N in M . However, it is well-known that all maximal quasi h -pure essential extensions are not necessarily h -pure in M .

A submodule N of a $QTAG$ -module M is called h -purifiable in M if there exists a submodule K of M minimal among the h -pure submodules of M containing N . Such K is called h -pure hull of N in M .

A submodule N of a $QTAG$ -module M is called a kV -submodule of M if there exists an integer k such that $N^t(M) \cong N_t(M), \forall t \geq k$. If $k = 0$, then N is a V -submodule of M .

With the aid of the above discussion we give the following definition.

Definition 2.1. A submodule N of a $QTAG$ -module M is said to be strongly h -purifiable with quasi h -pure in M if N is kV -submodule in M and all maximal quasi h -pure essential extensions of $N \cap H_k(M)$ in $H_k(M)$ are h -pure in $H_k(M)$ for some non-negative integer k .

Remark 2.1. Clearly, strongly h -purifiable submodules imply h -purifiable.

Khan [6] introduced the concept of kernel of h -purity for $QTAG$ -module: If N is a submodule of a $QTAG$ -module M , then N is called kernel of h -purity if all h -neat hulls of N are h -pure submodules of M .

But, since kernel of h -purity are h -purifiable submodules, so here we defining the following:

Definition 2.2. If N is a submodule of a $QTAG$ -module M , then N is called a kernel of h -purifiability in M if every h -neat hull of N is h -purifiable in M .

Now we are able to prove the following.

Proposition 2.1. Let N be a submodule of a $QTAG$ -module M such that N is quasi h -pure in M and if N is a kernel of h -purifiability in M , then N is strongly h -purifiable in M .

Proof. Let P be a maximal quasi h -pure essential extension of N in M . Then we have $P \supset N$ and $Soc(P) = Soc(N)$. Let Q be an h -neat hull of P , then Q is h -neat hull of N . By hypothesis, there exists an h -pure hull R of Q in M . By [11, Lemma 4], there exists a non-negative integer k such that $Soc(H_k(R)) \subset Soc(Q) = Soc(P)$. Therefore, P is h -purifiable in M . Since P is maximal quasi h -pure in M , P is h -pure in M and we are done. \square

Regarding the above proposition, the following immediately follows.

Proposition 2.2. For some non-negative integer k , if $N \cap H_k(M)$ is h -dense in M or if $Soc(H_t(M/N)) = (Soc(H_t(M)) + N)/N$ for every $t \geq k$, then N is strongly h -purifiable with quasi h -pure in M .

To develop the study, we need the following proposition.

Proposition 2.3. Let N be a submodule of a $QTAG$ -module M such that N is h -purifiable in M and let C and D be h -pure hulls of N in M , then $Soc(H_t(C/N)) \cong Soc(H_t(D/N))$ for every ordinal $t \leq \omega$.

Proof. It is sufficient to prove in the case $t = \omega$. By [11, Lemma 4], we may consider a kV -submodule N of M such that $Q_k(M, N) = 0$ for all $k \geq 0$ and

$$\begin{aligned} Soc(H_t(M/N)) &= Soc(H_t(C/N)) \oplus (Soc(H_t(M)) + N)/N, \\ &= Soc(H_t(D/N)) \oplus (Soc(H_t(M)) + N)/N \end{aligned}$$

for all $t \geq k$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} Soc(H_\omega(M/N)) &= Soc(H_\omega(C/N)) \oplus \cap_t [(Soc(H_t(M)) + N)/N], \\ &= Soc(H_\omega(D/N)) \oplus \cap_t [(Soc(H_t(M)) + N)/N] \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $Soc(H_\omega(C/N)) \cong Soc(H_\omega(D/N))$. \square

Along similar lines we have the following.

Definition 2.3. Let N be a submodule of a $QTAG$ -module M such that N is h -purifiable in M and C be an h -pure hull of N in M . For every ordinal $t \leq \omega$, we denote the cardinality of $Soc(H_t(C/N))$ by

$$R_t(M, N) = g(Soc(H_t(C/N)))$$

and the cardinality of $Soc(H_t(M/N))/Soc(H_t(C/N))$ by

$$S_t(M, N) = g\left(\frac{Soc(H_t(M/N))}{Soc(H_t(C/N))}\right)$$

It is observed that

$$\left(\frac{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(M/N))}{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(C/N))} \right) = \left(\frac{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(M/N))}{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(D/N))} \right)$$

Therefore Proposition 2.3 and [18, Definition 2.3] also show that $R_t(M, N)$ and $S_t(M, N)$ do not depend on the choice of an h -pure hull of N in G and these are relative invariants of N in G . Further, these are extensions of invariants induced in [18].

Now we investigate some properties of quasi h -pure submodules.

Lemma 2.1. *Let N be quasi h -pure submodule of the QTAG-module M such that N is h -purifiable in M . If K is an h -pure hull of N in M with $a \in K \setminus N$ and $a' \in N$ where $d\left(\frac{aR}{a'R}\right) = 1$ and if $b \in \text{Soc}(M) \setminus K$, then the following are equivalent.*

- (i) $N + \langle a + b \rangle$ is quasi h -pure in M ;
- (ii) $H_{M/N}(a + N) \leq H_{M/N}(b + N)$ or $H_{M/N}(b + N) \geq \omega$.

Proof. Let $H_{M/N}(a + N) = m$ and $H_{M/N}(b + N) = n$, where m and n are ordinals. Suppose that (i) is satisfied. If $n < \omega$ and $n < m$, then there exists a finite ordinal k such that $n < k \leq m$. By [11, Lemma 4], we have

$$\text{Soc}(H_k(M/N)) = \text{Soc}(H_k(K/N)) \oplus (\text{Soc}(H_k(M) + N)/N)$$

Now consider $x \in M$, $y \in N$ and $z \in \text{Soc}H_k(M)$ such that $z = x' - a + y$ where $d\left(\frac{xR}{x'R}\right) = k$. Then by [7, Theorem 4.6] and hypothesis, we have

$$b - z \in \text{Soc}(N + \langle a + b \rangle + H_k(M)) = \text{Soc}(N + \langle a + b \rangle) + \text{Soc}(H_k(M)).$$

If $y + r(a + b) \in \text{Soc}(N + \langle a + b \rangle)$ where $y \in N$ and r is an integer, then $e(y + ra) = 1$ and $(y + ra) \in \text{Soc}(K) = \text{Soc}(N)$ [11, Lemma 4]. Therefore $e(r) < 1$ and $b - z \in \text{Soc}(N) + \text{Soc}(H_k(M))$.

On the other hand, since $N + \langle a \rangle$ is quasi h -pure in M by [7, Theorem 4.8], we have $z \in \text{Soc}(N + \langle a \rangle + H_k(M)) = \text{Soc}(N) + \text{Soc}(H_k(M))$. Hence $b + N \in (\text{Soc}(H_k(M)) + N)/N$. This is a contradiction. Therefore $m \leq n$ or $n \geq \omega$.

Conversely, suppose that (ii) satisfied. If $t \leq m$, then we have

$$\text{Soc}(N + \langle a + b \rangle + H_t(M)) = \text{Soc}(N + H_t(M)) = \text{Soc}(N) + \text{Soc}(H_t(M)).$$

Let $t > m$ and $c \in \text{Soc}(N + \langle a + b \rangle + H_t(M))$, then we have $c = y + r(a + b) + x'$ where $d\left(\frac{xR}{x'R}\right) = t$, $y \in N$, $x \in M$, and r is an integer. Since $N + \langle a \rangle$ is quasi h -pure in M , we have

$$y + ra + x' \in \text{Soc}(N + \langle a \rangle + H_t(M)) = \text{Soc}(N) + \text{Soc}(H_t(M))$$

where $d\left(\frac{xR}{x'R}\right) = t$ and $ra \in N + H_t(M)$. Therefore $e(r) < 1$ and $N + \langle a + b \rangle$ is quasi h -pure in M . \square

Combining the Lemma 2.1 and [7, Theorem 4.8], we derive the following.

Lemma 2.2. *Let N be quasi h -pure submodule of the QTAG-module M such that N is strongly h -purifiable in M . If K be an h -pure hull of N in M with $a \in K \setminus N$ and $a' \in N$ where $d\left(\frac{aR}{a'R}\right) = 1$ and if $b \in \text{Soc}(M) \setminus K$ such that $H_{M/N}(a + N) \leq H_{M/N}(b + N)$ or $H_{M/N}(b + N) \geq \omega$, then there exists an h -pure hull L of N in M such that $a \notin L$.*

Proof. By Lemma 2.1, $N + \langle a + b \rangle$ is quasi h -pure in M and $\text{Soc}(N + \langle a + b \rangle) = \text{Soc}(N)$. Let L be a maximal quasi h -pure essential extension of $N + \langle a + b \rangle$, then L is an h -pure hull of N in M . If $a \in L$, then $b \in L$. Since $\text{Soc}(L) = \text{Soc}(N)$ by [11, Lemma 4], we have $b \in \text{Soc}(N)$. This is a contradiction. Therefore $a \notin L$. \square

We will have use for the following necessary condition.

Theorem 2.1. *Let N be a submodule of a QTAG-module M such that N is h -purifiable in M and if N is an intersection of finitely many h -pure hull of M . Then for every ordinal $t \leq \omega$, there exists a positive integer k_t such that*

$$R_t(M, N) \leq k_t S_t(M, N)$$

Proof. If $t < \omega$, then the result follows by [11, Theorem 11]. Let $N = \bigcap_{i=1}^k L_i$, where each L_i is an h -pure hull of N containing M for $1 \leq i \leq k$. Now we may put $K_n = \bigcap_{i=1}^n \text{Soc}(H_\omega(L_i/N))$, then we have

$$R_\omega(M, N) = \sum_{n=1}^{k-1} g(K_n/K_{n+1}).$$

As

$$\frac{K_n}{K_{n+1}} = \frac{K_n}{K_n \cap \text{Soc}(H_\omega(L_{n+1}/N))} \cong \frac{K_n + \text{Soc}(H_\omega(L_{n+1}/N))}{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(L_{n+1}/N))} \subset \frac{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(M/N))}{\text{Soc}(H_\omega(L_{n+1}/N))}.$$

Then for every ordinal $t \leq \omega$, there exists a positive integer k_t such that

$$R_t(M, N) \leq k_t S_t(M, N).$$

\square

We are now in the position to prove the following theorem.

Theorem 2.2. *Let N be quasi h -pure submodule of the QTAG-module M such that N is strongly h -purifiable in M . Then N is an intersection of finitely many h -pure hulls of N in M if and only if, for every ordinal $t \leq \omega$, there exists a positive integer k_t such that*

$$R_t(M, N) \leq k_t S_t(M, N)$$

Proof. The necessity follows from Theorem 2.1 above.

Conversely suppose that the condition holds. We have three cases to consider.

(1) For every $t < \omega$, $S_t(M, N)$ is infinite and there exists a strictly increasing sequence $\{t_i\}_{i=0}^\infty$ with $t_0 = 0$ such that $S_{t_i}(M, N) = S_{t_{i+1}-1}(M, N)$ for every $i < \omega$.

(2) For every $t < \omega$, $S_t(M, N)$ is infinite and there exists a finite ordinal m such that $S_t(M, N) = S_{t+1}(M, N)$ for every $t \geq m$. Then $S_\omega(M, N) = S_m(M, N)$.

(3) There exists a finite ordinal m such that $S_m(M, N)$ is finite.

Let L be an h -pure hull of N in M and let $Soc(H_t(L/N)) = N^t \oplus Soc(H_{t+1}(L/N))$ where N^t is a subsocle of L/N for $0 \leq t < \omega$. Put $N^\omega = \bigoplus_t N^t = \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \langle a_\lambda + N \rangle$ and $Soc(L/N) = Soc(H_\omega(L/N)) \oplus N^\omega \oplus L'$. We may be define $A = \{a_\lambda + N \mid \lambda \in \Lambda\}$, $B_t = (Soc(H_t(M)) + N)/N$ such that $B_t = J_t \oplus B_{t+1}$, and J^t be a set of basis of J_t for every $t < \omega$. Let A^ω and B^ω be sets of basis of $Soc(H_\omega(L/N))$ and $\bigcap_{t=0}^{\infty} B_t$ respectively.

Case 1. Note that $R_t(M, N) \leq S_t(M, N)$ for every $t < \omega$. Then there exists an injection $f : A \rightarrow \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} J^i$ such that $f(a_\lambda + N) = b_\lambda + N \in \bigcup_{i=0}^{\infty} J^i$ where $a_\lambda + N \in N^t$, for every $t < \omega$. Let $K_\omega/N = \bigoplus_{\lambda \in \Lambda} \langle a_\lambda + b_\lambda + N \rangle$.

First, we prove that L_ω is quasi h -pure in M . Let $c \in Soc(L_\omega + H_t(M))$, then we can write $c = a + b + y + x'$ where $d\left(\frac{xR}{x'R}\right) = t$, $H_{M/N}(a + N) \leq H_{x/N}(b + N)$, $a \in L, b \in Soc(M)$, $x \in M$ and $y \in N$. Since $N + \langle a + b \rangle$ is quasi h -pure in M by Lemma 2.1, we have $c \in Soc(N + \langle a + b \rangle + H_t(M)) = Soc(N) + Soc(H_t(M))$. Therefore L_ω is quasi h -pure in M and there exists an h -pure hull K of N containing L_ω .

Next, we prove that $(L' \oplus N^\omega) \cap K/N = 0$. Let $\bar{z} \in (L' \oplus N^\omega) \cap K/N$, then $H_{M/N}(\bar{z}) = n$, for some finite ordinal n . Since $\bar{z} \in Soc(K/N) = Soc(L_\omega/N)$, we have $\bar{z} = a_1 + b + N$, where $a_1 + N \in L/Soc(N)$ with $H_{M/N}(a_1 + N) = n$ and $b + N \in (Soc(M) + N)/N$ with $H_{M/N}(b + N) \geq n$. Then $b + N \in Soc(L/N)$ and this is a contradiction. Therefore $(L' \oplus N^\omega) \cap K/N = 0$.

On the other hand, consider $Soc(H_\omega(L/N)) = \bigoplus_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \langle a_\gamma + N \rangle$ and $A_\omega = \{a_\gamma + N \mid \gamma \in \Gamma\}$. Suppose that Γ is finite. By Lemma 2.2, for every $\gamma \in \Gamma$, there exists an h -pure hull K_γ of N in M such that $a_\gamma + N \notin K_\gamma/N$. Therefore we have $K \cap (\bigcap_{\gamma \in \Gamma} K_\gamma) \cap L = N$. If Γ is infinite, then $R_\omega(M, N) \leq S_\omega(M, N)$. Then there exists an injection $g : A^\omega \rightarrow B^\omega$ such that $g(a_\gamma + N) = b_\gamma + N$ and $L_1/N = \bigoplus \langle a_\gamma + b_\gamma + N \mid \gamma \in \Gamma \rangle$. Therefore L_1 is quasi h -pure in M and there exists an h -pure hull K_1 of N in M such that $K_1/N \cap Soc(H_\omega(L/N)) = 0$. Hence $K_1 \cap K \cap L = N$.

Case 2. Assume that

$$Soc(H_m(L/N)) = \bigoplus_{\theta \in \Theta} \langle u_\theta + N \rangle, \quad A^m = \{u_\theta + N \mid \theta \in \Theta\},$$

$$\bigoplus_{i=0}^{m-1} N^i = \bigoplus_{\phi \in \Phi} \langle a_\phi + N \rangle, \quad \text{and } A' = \{a_\phi + N \mid \phi \in \Phi\}.$$

By hypothesis, it follows that $R_t(M, N) \leq S_t(M, N)$ for every $t < \omega$. Then there exists an injection $h : (A' \cup A^m) \rightarrow (\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-1} J^i) \cup B_\omega$ satisfying the following conditions: for every $0 \leq t < m$,

$$h(a_\phi + N) = b_\phi + N \in \bigcup_{i=t}^{m-1} J^i, \quad \text{if } a_\phi + N \in N^t \quad \text{and} \quad h(u_\theta + N) = b_\theta + N \in B^\omega, \quad \text{if } u_\theta + N \in A^m.$$

Put $L_2/N = \bigoplus_{\phi \in \Phi, \theta \in \Theta} \langle a_\phi + b_\phi + N, u_\theta + b_\theta + N \rangle$. By Case 1, L_2 is quasi h -pure in M and there exists an h -pure hull K_2 of N in M containing L_2 such that $K_2 \cap L = N$.

Case 3. We have $R_t(M, N) \leq S_t(M, N)$ for every $t < m$. Let A' and A^m be two sets defined in Case 2. Then there exists an injection $\ell : A' \rightarrow \bigcup_{i=0}^{m-1} J^i$ such that $\ell(a_\phi + N) = b_\phi + N \in \bigcup_{i=t}^{m-1} J^i$, if $a_\phi + N \in A^t$ for every $t < m$. Put $L_3/N = \bigoplus_{\phi \in \Phi} \langle a_\phi + b_\phi + N \rangle$. By Case 1, L_3 is also quasi h -pure in M and there exists an h -pure hull K_3 of N in M containing L_3 such that $K_3/N \cap \bigoplus_{i=0}^{m-1} A^i = 0$. Let B^m be a set of basis of B_m . For every $u_\theta + N \in A^m$, there exists an element $b_\theta + N \in B^m$ such that $H_{M/N}(u_\theta + N) \leq H_{M/N}(b_\theta + N)$. By Lemma 2.2, for every $\theta \in \Theta$, there exists an h -pure hull K_θ of N in M such that $K_\theta/N \cap \langle u_\theta + N \rangle = 0$. Since Θ is finite, N is an intersection of finitely many h -pure hulls of N in M . \square

The following lemma is one of the main ingredient in the proof of our main result.

Lemma 2.3. *Let N be a kV -submodule of the QTAG-module M such that N is h -purifiable in M . Then for some positive integer k , we have*

$$R_{t+k}(M, N) = R_t(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M)) \text{ and } S_{t+k}(M, N) = S_t(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M)),$$

for every ordinal $t < \omega$. Moreover, we have

$$R_\omega(M, N) = R_\omega(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M)) \text{ and } S_\omega(M, N) = S_\omega(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M)).$$

Proof. Let L be an h -pure hull of N in M , then $H_k(L)$ is an h -pure hull of $N \cap H_k(M)$ in $H_k(M)$. Therefore we have

$$\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M/N)) = \text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(L/N)) \oplus (\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + N)/N)$$

and

$$\text{Soc}\left(H_t\left(\frac{H_k(M)}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right)\right) = \text{Soc}\left(H_t\left(\frac{H_k(L)}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right)\right) \oplus \left(\frac{H_{t+k}(M) + (N \cap H_k(M))}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right)$$

for every $t \geq 0$. By [18, Lemma 3.3], it follows that

$$\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(L/N)) \cong \text{Soc}\left(H_t\left(\frac{H_k(L)}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right)\right) \text{ and } R_{t+k}(M, N) = R_t(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M)) \text{ for every } t \geq 0.$$

Moreover, we have $R_\omega(M, N) = R_\omega(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M))$.

On the other hand, we have

$$\left(\frac{\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + (N \cap H_k(M)))}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right) = \left(\frac{(\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + N) \cap H_k(M))}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right).$$

Put $U = \text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + N)$, $V = N$, and $W = H_k(M)$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} (U \cap W) + V &= (\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + N) \cap H_k(M)) + N \\ &= \text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + N) \\ &= U \end{aligned}$$

By Dedekind short exact sequence, we have

$$\left(\frac{\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + (N \cap H_k(M)))}{N \cap H_k(M)}\right) = \left(\frac{\text{Soc}(H_{t+k}(M) + N)}{N}\right).$$

Therefore $S_{t+k}(M, N) = S_t(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M))$ for every $t \geq 0$. Moreover we have $S_\omega(M, N) = S_\omega(H_k(M), N \cap H_k(M))$. \square

We are now ready to proceed by proving the main result.

Theorem 2.3. *Let N be a submodule of the QTAG-module M such that N is strongly h -purifiable with quasi h -pure in M . Then N is an intersection of finitely many h -pure hulls of N in M if and only if, for some nonnegative integer n and for every ordinal $t = 0$ or $n \leq t \leq \omega$, there exists a positive integer k_t such that*

$$R_t(M, N) \leq k_t S_t(M, N)$$

Proof. By Theorem 2.2, Lemma 2.3 and [11, Theorem 11], the necessity is immediate.

Conversely, suppose that the condition holds. We may define $N \cap H_n(M) = \bigcap_{i=1}^k L_i$ where L_i is an h -pure hull of $N \cap H_n(M)$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$. By [7, Proposition 4.10], we can extend $N + L_i$ to be an h -pure submodules P_i of M for $1 \leq i \leq k$. By [11, Theorem 11], we have $N = (\bigcap_{i=1}^k P_i) \cap (\bigcap_{j=1}^s Q_j)$ where Q_j is an h -pure hull of N in M for $1 \leq j \leq s$. Then, since N is h -purifiable in P_i and we are done. \square

3. Open Problems

In closing, we pose the following questions of interest:

Problem 3.1. Can torsion-free strongly h -purifiable be characterized by certain numerical invariants?

Problem 3.2. Does there exist a strongly h -purifiable which is not kV -submodules?

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